

Articles series, part 2: Tolerances in implant dentistry. Effects of tolerances on the implant performance: an urgent warring about multiple non-continuous implant abutment connections` contacts.

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Abstract

Tolerances are present as an integral part of the modern manufacturing. We should deal with as an unavoidable phenomenon that could ruin the treatment if we choose the poor designs criteria. Multiple implant abutment connections are strongly prohibited due to the damaging interferences that produced by the misfitting of the abutment inside of the implant. We want to demonstrate the mechanical effect of negligence of tolerances on the performance of the implant abutment connections. Mismatch when occur could leave a gap at the upper connection or at the lower connection. Engineering descriptions are highly desirable in these conditions.

Keywords: Bone, Biomechanics, dental implants, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of bone, jaws weakeners, jaw stiffeners.

Introduction

In our previous paper we had demonstrated the root of the tolerance's phenomena (1). It could be occurred at every dimension vector in the global coordination system. (1) Perfect matching of the implant parts is happened only in the theoretical assumptions (2). We want to answer the question about what will happen with different tolerances scenarios.

Figure 1 Simply we may have shorter or wider abutment or any combination with possibility of the this at any side

Figure 2 We could have an increase in the dimensions at any region

The mis-match could happen at any region as different region machining need retraction of the tool from a certain position and attain a new position

In the case of dental implants, most companies produce the contact of the abutment and the implant at an inclined region we had called cone which will be single continuous region. Som manufacturers (such as in Arum implant, Dio implant and Dentium) produce multiple contacts at different levels. If we consider tolerances, we may get undersized, normal sized or oversized feature

We have these possibilities with the systems of single continuous implant- abutment connections:

1. We may have wide abutment and narrow implant.
2. We may have wide abutment and wide implant.
3. We may have wide abutment and perfect implant.
4. We may have narrow abutment and narrow implant.
5. We may have narrow abutment and wide implant.
6. We may have narrow abutment and perfect implant.
7. We may have perfect abutment and narrow implant.
8. We may have perfect abutment and wide implant.
9. We may have perfect abutment and perfect implant.

In any case of the diameter of the abutment is larger than the implant, this will result in higher abutment position and vice versa when we have narrower abutment and we will have lower implant position. Anyhow we will not get any perfect relationship between the implant and the abutment as the manufacturing will have some sort of deviation from the drawings (3)

When we have tolerances in the drawing inside the virtual environment, it is ironically of the implant companies to claim perfections in their productions

Figure 3 Prescence of oversized contact will result in higher position of the abutment and vice versa

The tolerances will affect the position of the abutment inside the implant. First figure is lower seated abutment and the middle is perfect and the third had an increase indicated by the green zone. We have here a single variable. In the case of narrower upper region there will be seating in the upper region as this will lead to gap at the upper region where contact should be occurred. This had been witnessed clearly in the scan bodies (4)

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Figure 4 In the reality, if there's a contact in the lower region there will be never a contact at the upper region and vice versa

In the case of dual contact between the implant and the abutment we will have 81 combinations

No.	Abutment Upper	Abutment Lower	Implant Upper	Implant Lower
1	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower
2	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower	Wider
3	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect
4	Narrower	Narrower	Wider	Narrower
5	Narrower	Narrower	Wider	Wider
6	Narrower	Narrower	Wider	Perfect
7	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower
8	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect	Wider
9	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect
10	Narrower	Wider	Narrower	Narrower
11	Narrower	Wider	Narrower	Wider
12	Narrower	Wider	Narrower	Perfect
13	Narrower	Wider	Wider	Narrower
14	Narrower	Wider	Wider	Wider
15	Narrower	Wider	Wider	Perfect
16	Narrower	Wider	Perfect	Narrower
17	Narrower	Wider	Perfect	Wider

18	Narrower	Wider	Perfect	Perfect
19	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower
20	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower	Wider
21	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect
22	Narrower	Perfect	Wider	Narrower
23	Narrower	Perfect	Wider	Wider
24	Narrower	Perfect	Wider	Perfect
25	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower
26	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect	Wider
27	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect
28	Wider	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower
29	Wider	Narrower	Narrower	Wider
30	Wider	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect
31	Wider	Narrower	Wider	Narrower
32	Wider	Narrower	Wider	Wider
33	Wider	Narrower	Wider	Perfect
34	Wider	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower
35	Wider	Narrower	Perfect	Wider

36	Wider	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect
37	Wider	Wider	Narrower	Narrower
38	Wider	Wider	Narrower	Wider
39	Wider	Wider	Narrower	Perfect
40	Wider	Wider	Wider	Narrower
41	Wider	Wider	Wider	Wider
42	Wider	Wider	Wider	Perfect
43	Wider	Wider	Perfect	Narrower
44	Wider	Wider	Perfect	Wider
45	Wider	Wider	Perfect	Perfect
46	Wider	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower
47	Wider	Perfect	Narrower	Wider
48	Wider	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect
49	Wider	Perfect	Wider	Narrower
50	Wider	Perfect	Wider	Wider
51	Wider	Perfect	Wider	Perfect
52	Wider	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower
53	Wider	Perfect	Perfect	Wider
54	Wider	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect
55	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower	Narrower
56	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower	Wider
57	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower	Perfect
58	Perfect	Narrower	Wider	Narrower

59	Perfect	Narrower	Wider	Wider
60	Perfect	Narrower	Wider	Perfect
61	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect	Narrower
62	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect	Wider
63	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect	Perfect
64	Perfect	Wider	Narrower	Narrower
65	Perfect	Wider	Narrower	Wider
66	Perfect	Wider	Narrower	Perfect
67	Perfect	Wider	Wider	Narrower
68	Perfect	Wider	Wider	Wider
69	Perfect	Wider	Wider	Perfect
70	Perfect	Wider	Perfect	Narrower
71	Perfect	Wider	Perfect	Wider
72	Perfect	Wider	Perfect	Perfect
73	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower	Narrower
74	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower	Wider
75	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower	Perfect
76	Perfect	Perfect	Wider	Narrower
77	Perfect	Perfect	Wider	Wider
78	Perfect	Perfect	Wider	Perfect
79	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect	Narrower
80	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect	Wider
81	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect	Perfect

Any narrowing in the lower region due to wider abutment or narrower implant will affect the upper region which produce catastrophic results. Any widening of the abutment or narrowing in the upper region of the abutment will result in early seating which acceptable condition which already happening in the present systems. There are many commercial systems featuring this point, dual contact which is totally different from dual contact at horizontal load we had presented in our previous paper (5)

Methods

Figure 5 Arum implant system as well as DIO implant system are both Korean and entitle the feature of multiple contact between the implant and the abutment

Figure 6 DIO is another implant system that feature this feature of multiple contacts between the implant and the abutment

Figure 7 It is not comparable to the previous feature. It is more impossible to machine such feature with even acceptable tolerances

The successful achievement of a Morse lock and cold weld seal in the implant-prosthetic connection depends on high precision machining. A perfect Morse connection will result in a structural integrity and strength that will be as if the 2 parts were fused together and thus will practically eliminate the gap between the implant and the abutment. Accordingly, the C-TECH components are machined to a tolerance of within 10 microns.

This mechanical fusion of the prosthetic part and the implant has 2 important benefits: prevention of the bacterial colonization of the gap, which can lead to bone loss around the implant; the elimination of micro-movements between the implant and abutment and the consequent screw loosening which can lead to prosthetic failure.

The SEM photos on the right show different magnifications of the tight abutment and implant connection. The final photo at the bottom, at 1000 X magnification, shows a fine line where the abutment and the implant meet. This practically nonexistent gap is less than the 1,5 microns.

Figure 8 we should emphasize upon the fact that the machining of the hex with taper is impossible to be with tighter tolerances due to the fact that the circular cone is much more practical. These features are the worst features and we hadn't simulated them although we had investigated them in the 1st paper of this series.

C-TECH implant claims that the tolerances is around 10 microns which is too much for 2 contacts as well as it is impossible to produce even a symmetrical hex at the abutment which is also impossible to fit perfectly inside the implant. Machining of such feature is via staged steps which is even worse than that in the case of DIO implant or Arum implant

We will study these models

- Only upper perfect model with the removal of the lower contact cone as this is the situation of the vast majority of the implant systems
- Perfect model at upper and lower
- Narrower upper region
- Narrower lower region

The chosen tolerances will be 10 microns although tolerances had been found to reach 250microns in the sone of the can bodies where precision is an integral perquisite of production (6). Accordingly, we assume that the gap might be 20 microns due to presence of tolerances at the implant and abatement at the same time which highly possible. (7) Our engineering model had been retrieved from the Arum implant system. Material properties had been mentioned in our previous papers (8)

Next are the criteria that is used to make a range of the graph's legends

1. von mises $1e9 - 1e8$
2. displacement abut .01 - .008

3. displacement only implant $2e-2$ - $8e-3$
4. x field .1 - .005
5. contact pressure abutment $1e8$ - $5e5$
6. contact pressure arrows $3e8$ - $1e6$
7. strain $3e-3$ - $1e-7$

Results

For the connecting screw criteria

- upper perfect lower gap

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	19.5	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	379.23	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.02358	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

- upper gap and lower perfect contact

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	57.579	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	438.93	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.0036229	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

- upper and lower perfect contact

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	28.047	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	345.98	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.041551	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

- upper perfect contact but without lower contact

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	19.608	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	394.24	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.018325	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

The highest stress on the screw is happening at the systems with claimed dual contact but the reality is not due to the effect of tolerances

Figure 9 Y field displacement Upper gap and lower contact

Figure 10 Y field of the displacement upper perfect contact and lower gap

Figure 11 Y field of the displacement of both upper and lower perfect contact

Figure 12 Y filed of displacement of the upper perfect contact and without lower contact

Figure 13 In the case of the perfect upper contact and no lower contact the pattern of dual contact is clearly seen

Figure 14 Only upper contact. The rotation of the abutment inside the implant must be noticed

Figure 15 We have surface to surface contact in the model with only upper contact

Figure 16 Only upper contact. Implant-abutment displacement ratio must be also evaluated

This is the ratio of different results were

- **No lower contact** Abutment max 0.1267mm and implant 0.05337mm
- **Up and lower perfect** Abut 0.1494mm Implant 0.05877mm
- **Upper gap due to tolerances and perfect lower contact** Abutment 0.1926mm Implant 0.05559mm
- **Lower gap due to tolerances and perfect upper contact** Abutment 0.1291mm Implant 0.05398mm

Figure 17 Only upper contact. X field of displacement is the best indicator of the implant or abutment rotation, especially the abutment

Figure 18 Only upper contact. Contact pressure is only happened in dual pattern

Figure 19 Only upper contact. Relative magnitude and location of the contact pressure

Figure 20 Strain of the only upper contact

All of the previous models are of only upper contacts without any lower contacts like in vast majority of implant systems. Next models are of the upper and lower contact where the condition is perfect which is not present in all systems

Figure 21 Von mises stress in the case of upper and lower perfect contact

Figure 22 Displacement in the case of upper and lower perfect contact. The rotation of the abutment inside the implant must be noticed

Figure 23 Upper and lower perfect contact. Implant abutment displacement must be also evaluated

Figure 24 Lower and upper contact are perfect. X field of displacement is the best indicator of the implant or abutment rotation, especially the abutment

Figure 25 Lower and upper contact. Contact pressure is only happened in dual pattern

Figure 26 Lower and upper Another representation of the contact pressure

Figure 27 Strain of the upper and lower perfect contact

All of the Previous upper and lower are perfect contact. Next models are of upper with initial gap of 20 microns

Figure 28 Von Mises stress of the model with upper gap and lower perfect contact

Figure 29 Displacement of the model with upper gap and only lower contact

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Figure 30 The side opposite to the force application site had point to surface contact

Figure 31 Displacement of the implant in the model with only lower contact

Figure 32 X displacement of the only upper model

Figure 33 Contact pressure of the abutment with the gap at the upper contact

Figure 34 Another graph of the contact pressure

Figure 35 We should emphasize that when the tolerances resulted in the gap in the upper region the resultant deformation will be

Figure 36 Strain of the only lower contact

All of the previous models are of only upper contact. Next models are of only upper contact and gap at lower region

Figure 37 Upper perfect and 20microns gap at lower. Von Mises stress graph

Figure 38 Upper perfect and 20 microns lower gap displacement

Figure 39 Implant abutment displacement ratio should always be evaluated

Figure 40 X field of displacement of the Upper perfect and lower had 20 microns gap

Figure 41 Contact pressure of only upper contact and 20 microns at lower

Figure 42 Contact pressure of the upper perfect contact and lower gap of 20 microns

Figure 43 Only upper perfect contact and lower 20 microns gap strain

In the previous models we can easily notice that that

- The tolerances could produced wide variation in the mechanical performance
- The worst model is the model that had gap at the upper proposed to be contact region
- The gap at the upper surface will render the surface-on-surface contact into point to surface contact
- These are pure mechanical points that will have no significant difference from the virtual model as it had been demonstrated by many papers
- The tolerances will produce some models that are highly unstable with high possibility of corrosion and release of Titanium wear products that will ultimately lead to bone loss (9) (10)

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Author profile

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